

Spectrophotometric Studies of Rhenium Complexes with 2-2'-Diaminodiphenyldisulphide

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Manuscript received 16 May 1980, revised 16 February 1981, accepted 30 March 1983

The reagent 2-2'-diaminodiphenyldisulphide produces a reddish brown complex with perrhenate in hydrochloric acid medium in presence of tin(II) chloride. Though the complex on extraction in chloroform shows no absorption maxima in the range 370-600 nm, the system obeys Beer's law with 2-22 ppm of rhenium at two arbitrarily chosen wavelengths of 420 and 450 nm and the molar absorptivity is found to be 1.08×10^4 and 7.82×10^4 , respectively. Study of composition by Job's and molar ratio methods indicates that the complex contains metal and reagent in the ratio 1 : 3. Stability constant of the complex has been evaluated by Leden's method ($\log K_{\text{overall}} = 10.225$), Rossoti Rossoti method ($\log K_{\text{overall}} = 9.844$) and Yatsimirskii method ($\log K_{\text{overall}} = 11.113$).

SOME organic thio compounds¹⁻¹⁵ have been used for spectrophotometric determination of rhenium. Some of these investigations are incomplete so far as their full spectrophotometric studies are concerned and hardly provide any information regarding the composition and the stability constants of the complexes formed. 2-2'-Diaminodiphenyldisulphide is found to form a reddish-brown complex with ReO_4^- reduced by SnCl_2 in HCl medium. Preliminary investigations show that not only the sensitivity of the colour is comparable with the other rhenium ligand systems⁴⁻¹⁵, but the specificity is much improved (high tolerance limit to common metal ions and WO_4^{2-}). We report here the details of the spectrophotometric analysis as well as the composition and the stability of the complex formed by the above reagent with rhenium.

Experimental

A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with 10 mm quartz transmission cells was used.

A standard rhenium(VII) solution was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed quantity of potassium perrhenate (Johnson Matthey) in double distilled water. The solution was standardised by Nitron's method¹⁴. A 0.3% (w/v) solution of 2-2'-diaminodiphenyldisulphide was prepared in absolute ethanol. 0.3635 M SnCl_2 solution was prepared in 1 N HCl.

Solutions of other ions were prepared from their chlorides, sulphates or from their sodium, potassium or ammonium salts and were standardised according to respective conventional methods. All other chemicals were of the highest degree of purity.

Recommended procedure :

5 ml of 0.3% (w/v) reagent solution in absolute ethanol was added to a standard solution of perrhenate, containing 1 ml of 0.25 mg/ml rhenium in a beaker, followed by 2 ml of 0.353 M tin(II) chloride

solution and hydrochloric acid to maintain the final acidity between 0.64 and 1.6 N. The solution was diluted to 25 ml with measured quantity of water and ethanol in the ratio 1 : 1. The mixture was then warmed for 5 min at 60-65°, cooled, transferred to a separating funnel and extracted with 12 ml chloroform after shaking for 10 min. The organic extract was taken over anhydrous sodium sulphate in a 50 ml beaker and transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask after drying. The aqueous phase was washed with chloroform (2 × 5 ml) and washing combined with the previous extract, after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The final volume was made upto 25 ml with chloroform. A reagent blank without rhenium was also prepared. The reagent had no absorbance at and above 400 nm. The absorbance of the reddish brown complex was measured at wavelengths 360-650 nm against a reagent blank. The system did not show any maximum absorption. Hence subsequent measurements were done at two arbitrarily chosen wavelengths of 420 and 450 nm.

Results and Discussion

Complete extraction of the complex in chloroform took only 10 min and the extract was stable for more than 24 hr. Addition of 2.5 ml of 3% reagent solution in alcohol produces full colour intensity with 10 ppm rhenium. Addition of more reagent had no adverse effect and so 5 ml of the reagent solution was used in all further tests. The optimum acid concentration for maximum colour development was 0.64-1.6 N in hydrochloric acid. Addition of 1 or 2 ml of 0.3 M tin(II) chloride solution suffices for 10 ppm of rhenium but always tin(II) chloride should be added before the addition of the reagent since addition in the reverse order resulted in the fading of the colour intensity. As the reduction has been carried out at 0.64-1.6 N HCl with excess of tin(II) chloride solution, the

perrhenate has undergone reduction to the +4 oxidation state. The 2-2'-diaminodiphenyldisulphide (DDD) complex of rhenium(IV) was extractable in chloroform and might possibly be a neutral complex with the probable composition of $[\text{ReO}(\text{DDD})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ where the reagent behaved as a monodentate ligand coordinating through nitrogen. The variation in the values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$ as obtained by different methods showed slight deviation from a regular decreasing trend. In all the cases, the differences in logarithmic terms were too small to be accounted for, but it indicated that the complexes are formed almost simultaneously.

Beer's law, optimum range, sensitivity and molar absorptivity :

Test solutions with different concentrations of rhenium were prepared by the recommended procedure. The system adheres to Beer's law from 2-22 ppm of rhenium at 420 nm and 450 nm.

The Ringbom's¹⁸ optimal concentration range for measurement was found to be 2.5-13.5 ppm at 420 nm and 3-13.5 ppm at 450 nm

Sandell sensitivities¹⁹ and molar absorptivities (calculated from Beer's law values) were $0.0166 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and 1.08×10^4 at 420 nm and $0.0424 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and 7.82×10^3 at 450 nm, respectively.

Effect of diverse ions :

The effect of diverse ions on the determination of rhenium was studied by adding 400 ppm of the ion in question to a solution containing 10 ppm of rhenium as ReO_4^- with the recommended procedure. Except for molybdenum, ferrous, platinum, palladium and vanadium the method is free from interferences. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Composition of the complex and stepwise formation constants :

Equimolar solutions of perrhenate and 2-2'-diaminodiphenyldisulphide ($5.37 \times 10^{-4} M$) were used to find the metal-ligand ratio by Job's method of continuous variation¹⁷ and mole ratio method¹⁹. Absorbances of three sets of complementary solutions were measured after extraction by the recommended procedure. The results showed the existence of 1 : 3 complex.

The procedure for evaluation of the stepwise formation constants was examined by proper extension of Leden's method and verified by the method of Rossotti and Rossotti.

Leden's method : The successive stability constants obtained by considering the degree of complex formation are given below. The term have their usual significance²⁰.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE COLOROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Re (10 PPM)

Ion	Amount tolerated (ppm)		Ion	Amount tolerated (ppm)	
	420 nm	450 nm		420 nm	450 nm
W(VI)	400	400	Zn(II)	400	400
U(VI)	400	400	Cd(II)	400	400
Ti(VI)	400	400	Co(II)	400	400
Mo(VI)	8	8	Tartrate	Interfere	Interfere
V(V)	Interfere	Interfere	Citrate	400	400
Ni(II)	400	400	EDTA	400	400
Mn(II)	400	400	Oxalate	400	400
Cu(II)	400	400	Phosphate	400	400
Pt(IV)	Interfere	Interfere	Sulphate	400	400
Pd(II)	Interfere	Interfere	Fluoride	Interfere	Interfere
Fe(II)	Interfere	Interfere	BO_2^-	Interfere	Interfere
Ir(II)	400	400	NO_2^-	400	400

Fig. 1. Leden's method.

$$\lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \Psi_1 = \lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \frac{\phi - 1}{L} = \beta_1 = K_1 = 1.0 \times 10^3 \quad (\text{Fig 1})$$

$$\lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \Psi_2 = \lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Psi_1 - \beta_1}{L} = \beta_2 = 1.40 \times 10^6 = K_2 = 1.40 \times 10^3 \quad (\text{Fig 1})$$

$$\lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \Psi_3 = \lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Psi_2 - \beta_2}{L} = \beta_3 = 1.70 \times 10^6 = K_3 = 1.20 \times 10^4 \quad (\text{Fig 1})$$

Rossotti and Rossotti's method²¹: This method was applied by assuming that the first complex exists in solutions of lower free ligand concentrations. The values of ϵ_1 and β_1 determined by the graphical extrapolation method are as follows

$$\epsilon_2 \beta_1 = 1.4 \times 10^3 \quad \beta_1 = 1.0 \times 10^4 \quad (\text{Fig. 2})$$

These values of ϵ_1 and β_1 were combined with the data for solutions of slightly higher ligand

concentrations to obtain the values of ϵ_2 and β_2 .

$$\epsilon_2 = 3.10 \times 10^3 \quad \beta_2 = 4.0 \times 10^6 \quad \text{therefore } K_2 = 2.85 \times 10^3 \quad (\text{Fig. 2})$$

These values of ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 and β_1 , β_2 were combined with the data for solutions of slightly higher ligand concentrations to obtain the values of ϵ_3 and β_3 .

$$\epsilon_3 = 3.1 \times 10^3 \quad \beta_3 = 0.35 \times 10^9 \quad \text{therefore } K_3 = 1.75 \times 10^3 \quad (\text{Fig. 2})$$

Yatsimirskii's method: The different stepwise formation constants of this complex were found by constructing suitable functions in forms of intercepts obtained of zero ligand concentration in the manner stated earlier²⁰.

$$\lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} f_1 = \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \frac{e}{[L]} = a_1 \quad (\text{Fig. 3})$$

and $\lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_{i-1} - a_{i-1}}{[L]} = a_i$, where $i=2, 3$

Fig. 2. Rossotti-Rossotti method.

Fig. 3. Subsidiary function f_1 , f_2 and f_3 as a function of the free-ligand concentration.

Fig. 4. Molar extinction coefficient ϵ , g and g_1 as a function of y .

The values found were as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= 1.42 \times 10^7 \\ a_2 &= -0.50 \times 10^{11} \\ a_3 &= 0.5 \times 10^{15} \end{aligned}$$

The curve to get values for a_1 , a_2 , a_3 is given in Fig. 3

$$\lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} \bar{e} = b_1 = 4.40 \times 10^3 \quad \text{where } Y = \frac{1}{[L]}$$

$$\text{and } \lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} g_n = \frac{\bar{e} - b_i - 1}{Y} = b_i \quad \text{where } n=0, 1, 2; \quad i=2, 3, 4$$

The curves to get values for b_1 , b_2 , b_3 are shown in Fig. 4. The values found were as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} b_1 &= 4.4 \times 10^3 \\ b_2 &= -0.55 \\ b_3 &= 3.5 \end{aligned}$$

On solving the equations relating to a_1 , a_2 , a_3 and b_1 , b_2 and b_3 we get the stepwise formation constant values $K_1 = 0.72 \times 10^9$, $K_2 = 5.8 \times 10^4$ and $K_3 = 2.825 \times 10^4$.

TABLE 2—OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANT AND STEPWISE FORMATION CONSTANT OF THE COMPLEX AT 27°

Methods	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_3$	$\log K_{\text{overall}}$
Leden	3.00	3.15	4.08	10.23
Rossotti-Rossotti	3.15	3.46	3.24	9.84
Yatsimirskii	1.86	4.76	4.49	11.11

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